

FUZZY NEUTROSOPHIC REGULAR σ -BAIRE SPACES

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Abstract. In this paper, the concepts of fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets are introduced and studied. By means of fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets, the concepts of fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire spaces are introduced and several characterizations of fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire spaces are studied.

Keywords: Fuzzy neutrosophic dense set, Fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set, Fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -set, Fuzzy neutrosophic Regular σ -nowhere dense set, Fuzzy neutrosophic Regular σ - Baire Space and Fuzzy neutrosophic Regular σ -first and second category.

1. Introduction

The fuzzy idea was invaded all branches of science as far back as the presentation of fuzzy sets by L. A. Zadeh [17]. The important concept of fuzzy topological space was offered by C.L. Chang [3]. The idea of fuzzy σ - Baire Spaces was introduced by G. Thangaraj and E. Poongothai [10]. The concept of neutrosophic sets was defined with membership, non-membership and indeterminacy degrees. In 2017, Veereswari [16] introduced fuzzy neutrosophic topological spaces. The idea of fuzzy neutrosophic Baire spaces was introduced by E. Poongothai and E. Padmavathi [7].

In this paper, the concepts of fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets are introduced and studied. By means of fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets, the concepts of fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire spaces are introduced and several characterizations of fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire spaces are studied.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [2] A fy. neutrosophic set A on the universe of discourse X is defined as $A = \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle$, $x \in X$ where $T, I, F : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x), F_A(x) \leq 3$. With the condition $0 \leq T_{A^*}(x) + I_{A^*}(x), F_{A^*}(x) \leq 2$

Definition 2.2. [2] A fy. neutrosophic set A is a subset of a fy. neutrosophic set B (i.e.,) $A \subseteq B$ for all x if $T_A(x) \leq T_B(x)$, $I_A(x) \leq I_B(x)$, $F_A(x) \geq F_B(x)$

Definition 2.3. [2] Let X be a non-empty set, and $A = \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle$, $B = \langle x, T_B(x), I_B(x), F_B(x) \rangle$ be two fy. neutrosophic sets. Then

$$A \cup B = \langle x, \max(T_A(x), T_B(x)), \max(I_A(x), I_B(x)), \min(F_A(x), F_B(x)) \rangle$$

$$A \cap B = \langle x, \min(T_A(x), T_B(x)), \min(I_A(x), I_B(x)), \max(F_A(x), F_B(x)) \rangle$$

Definition 2.4. [2] The difference between two fy. neutrosophic sets A and B is defined as $A \setminus B(x) = \langle x, \min(T_A(x), F_B(x)), \min(I_A(x), 1 - I_B(x)), \max(F_A(x), T_B(x)) \rangle$

Definition 2.5. [2] A fy. neutrosophic set A over the universe X is said to be null or empty fy. neutrosophic set if $T_A(x) = 0$, $I_A(x) = 0$, $F_A(x) = 1$ for all $x \in X$. It is denoted by 0_N

Definition 2.6. [2] A fy. neutrosophic set A over the universe X is said to be absolute (universe) fy. neutrosophic set if $T_A(x) = 1$, $I_A(x) = 1$, $F_A(x) = 0$ for all $x \in X$. It is denoted by 1_N

Definition 2.7. [2] The complement of a fy. neutrosophic set A is denoted by A^C and is defined as $A^C = \langle x, T_{A^C}(x), I_{A^C}(x), F_{A^C}(x) \rangle$ where $T_{A^C}(x) = F_A(x)$, $I_{A^C}(x) = 1 - I_A(x)$, $F_{A^C}(x) = T_A(x)$. The complement of fy. neutrosophic set A can also be defined as $A^C = 1_N - A$.

Definition 2.8. [2] A fy. neutrosophic topology on a non-empty set X is a τ of fy. neutrosophic sets in X satisfying the following axioms.

- (i) $0_N, 1_N \in \tau$
- (ii) $A_1 \cap A_2 \in \tau$ for any $A_1, A_2 \in \tau$
- (iii) $\cup A_i \in \tau$ for any arbitrary family $\{A_i : i \in J\} \in \tau$

In this case the pair (X, τ) is called fy. neutrosophic top. space and any fy. neutrosophic set in τ is known as fy. neutrosophic open set in X

Definition 2.9. [1] The complement of a fy. neutrosophic set A in a fy. neutrosophic top. space (X, τ) is called fy. neutrosophic closed set in X .

Definition 2.10. [1] Let (X, τ) be a fy. neutrosophic top. space and $A = \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle$ be a fy. neutrosophic set in X . Then the closure and interior of

A are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{int}(A) &= \cup\{G : G \text{ is a fuzzy neutrosophic open set in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A\} \\ \text{cl}(A) &= \cap\{G : G \text{ is a fuzzy neutrosophic closed set in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq G\} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.11. [1] Let (X, τ) be a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space over X . Then (i) $\text{cl}(A^C) = (\text{int } A)^C$, (ii) $\text{int}(A^C) = (\text{cl } A)^C$

Definition 2.12. [7] A fy. neutrosophic set A_N in a fy. neutrosophic top. space (P, τ_N) is called a fy. neutrosophic F_σ -set if $A_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} A_{N_i}$, where $\overline{A_{N_i}} \in \tau_N$ for $i \in I$

Definition 2.13. [7] A fy. neutrosophic set A_N in a fy. neutrosophic top. space (P, τ_N) is called a fy. neutrosophic G_δ -set in (P, τ_N) if $A_N = \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} A_{N_i}$, where $A_{N_i} \in \tau_N$ for $i \in I$

Definition 2.14. [7] A fy. neutrosophic set A_N in a fy. neutrosophic top. space (P, τ_N) is called a fy. neutrosophic dense if there exist no $fnCS$ B_N in (P, τ_N) s.t $A_N \subset B_N \subset 1_X$. That is $fn(A_N)^- = 1_N$

Definition 2.15. [7] A fy. neutrosophic set A_N in a fy. neutrosophic top. space (P, τ_N) is called a fy. neutrosophic nowh. dense set if there exist no non zero $fnOS$ B_N in (P, τ_N) s.t $B_N \subset fn(A_N)^-$. That is $fn(((A_N)^-)^+) = 0_N$

Definition 2.16. [7] Let (P, τ_N) be a fy. neutrosophic top. space. A fy. neutrosophic set A_N in (P, τ_N) is called fy. neutrosophic one category set if $A_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} A_{N_i}$, where A_{N_i} 's are fy. neutrosophic nowh. dense sets in (P, τ_N) . Any other fy. neutrosophic set in (P, τ_N) is said to be of fy. neutrosophic two category.

Definition 2.17. [7] A fy. neutrosophic top. space (P, τ_N) is called fy. neutrosophic one category space if the fy. neutrosophic set 1_X is a fy. neutrosophic one category set in (P, τ_N) . That is $1_X = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} A_{N_i}$, where A_{N_i} 's are fy. neutrosophic nowh. dense sets in (P, τ_N) . Otherwise (P, τ_N) will be called a fy. neutrosophic two category space.

Definition 2.18. [4] Let (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space. A fuzzy neutrosophic Set λ_N in (X_N, T_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set if λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set in (X_N, T_N) such that $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$.

Definition 2.19. [4] Let (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space. A fuzzy neutrosophic set λ_N in (X_N, T_N) is called fuzzy neutrosophic σ - first category if $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$ Where λ_{N_i} 's are fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Any other fuzzy neutrosophic set in (X_N, T_N) is said to be fuzzy neutrosophic σ - second category in (X_N, T_N) .

Definition 2.20. [4] Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Then $1_N - \lambda_N$ is called a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -residual set in (X_N, T_N) .

Definition 2.21. [4] A fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) is called fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category if the fuzzy neutrosophic set 1_{X_N} is a fuzzy neutrosophic set σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) . That is $1_{X_N} = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$ Where λ_{N_i} 's are fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Otherwise (X_N, T_N) will be called a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -second category space.

Definition 2.22. [4] Let (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space then (X_N, T_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space if $\text{int}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$, where λ_{N_i} 's are fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) .

Theorem 2.23. [5] If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) , then λ_N is not a fuzzy neutrosophic dense set in (X_N, T_N) .

Theorem 2.24. [7] Let (P, τ_N) be a fy. neutrosophic top. space. Then the following are equivalent

- (1) (P, τ_N) is a fy. neutrosophic Baire space.
- (2) $fn(A_N)^+ = 0_N$, for every fy. neutrosophic one category set A_N in (P, τ_N) .
- (3) $fn(B_N)^+ = 1_N$, for every fy. neutrosophic re. set B_N in (P, τ_N) .

Definition 2.25. [7] Let A_N be a fy. neutrosophic one category set in (P, τ_N) . Then \bar{A}_N is called fy. neutrosophic re. set in (P, τ_N) .

Definition 2.26. [7] A fy. neutrosophic top. space (P, τ_N) is called fy. neutrosophic Baire space if $fn(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (A_{N_i}))^+ = 0_N$, where (A_{N_i}) 's are fy. neutrosophic nowh. dense sets in (P, τ_N) .

Theorem 2.27. [4] Let (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space. Then the following are equivalent

- (1) (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space.
- (2) $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$, for every fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set λ_N in (X_N, T_N) .
- (3) $cl(\mu_N) = 1_N$, for every fuzzy neutrosophic σ -residual set μ_N in (X_N, T_N) .

Definition 2.28. [9] A fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic submaximal space if for each fuzzy neutrosophic set A_N in (X, τ_N) such that $(A_N)^- = 1$ then $A_N \in \tau_N$ in (X, τ_N) . That is (X, τ_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic submaximal space if each fuzzy neutrosophic dense set in (X, τ_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic open set in (X, τ_N) .

Definition 2.29. [9] A fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic resolvable space if there exist a fuzzy neutrosophic dense set A_N in (X, τ_N) such that $(1 - A_N)^- = 1$. Otherwise, (X, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic irresolvable space.

Definition 2.30. [9] A fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic hyperconnected space if every non-null fuzzy neutrosophic open subset of (X, τ_N) is fuzzy neutrosophic dense in (X, τ_N) .

Definition 2.31. [9] A fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space if each fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -set in (X, τ_N) is fuzzy neutrosophic open set in (X, τ_N) .

Definition 2.32. [9] A fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic almost resolvable space if $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (A_{N_i}) = 1$, where (A_{N_i}) 's in (X, τ_N) are such that $(A_{N_i})^+ = 0$, otherwise, (X, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic almost irresolvable space.

3. FUZZY NEUTROSOPHIC REGULAR σ -NOWHERE DENSE SET

Definition 3.1. Let (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space. A fuzzy neutrosophic set λ_N in (X_N, T_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set if $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} cl(\lambda_{N_i})$, where $int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$.

Example 3.2. Let $X_N = \{a, b, c\}$. The fuzzy neutrosophic sets $\lambda_N, \mu_N, \gamma_N$ are defined on X_N as follows:

$\lambda_N : X_N \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined as $\lambda_N(a) = 0.5; \lambda_N(b) = 0.6; \lambda_N(c) = 0.7$

$\mu_N : X_N \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined as $\mu_N(a) = 0.6; \mu_N(b) = 0.5; \mu_N(c) = 0.4$

$\gamma_N : X_N \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined as $\gamma_N(a) = 0.4; \gamma_N(b) = 0.5; \gamma_N(c) = 0.6$

Then, $T_N = \{0_N, \lambda_N, \mu_N, \gamma_N, \lambda_N \vee \mu_N, \mu_N \vee \gamma_N, \lambda_N \wedge \mu_N, \lambda_N \wedge [\mu_N \vee \gamma_N], 1_N\}$ is clearly a fuzzy neutrosophic topology on X_N . Now, consider the following fuzzy neutrosophic sets defined on X_N .

$\alpha_N : X_N \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined as $\alpha_N(a) = 0.4, \alpha_N(b) = 0.6, \alpha_N(c) = 0.7$

$\beta_N : X_N \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined as $\beta_N(a) = 0.5, \beta_N(b) = 0.6, \beta_N(c) = 0.3$

$\delta_N : X_N \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is defined as $\delta_N(a) = 0.3, \delta_N(b) = 0.5, \delta_N(c) = 0.6$

Now, on computation, $int(\alpha_N) = 0_N, int(\beta_N) = 0_N, int(\delta_N) = 0_N$ and $cl(\delta_N) = 1_N - \mu_N, cl(\beta_N \wedge \delta_N) = 1_N - (\mu_N \vee \gamma_N)$. Then $cl(\delta_N) \vee cl(\beta_N \wedge \delta_N) = (1_N - \mu_N) \vee [1_N - (\mu_N \vee \delta_N)] = 1_N - \mu_N$. Hence $1_N - \mu_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) .

Proposition 3.3. If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) , then $1_N - \lambda_N = \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (\mu_{N_i})$, where $cl(\mu_{N_i}) = 1_N$.

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) . Then $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} cl(\lambda_{N_i})$, where $int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$. Now, $int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$ implies that $1_N - int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 1_N$ and hence we have $cl(1_N - \lambda_{N_i}) = 1_N$. Also, $1_N - \lambda_N = 1_N - \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} cl(\lambda_{N_i}) = \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} int(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})$, where $cl(1_N - \lambda_{N_i}) = 1_N$. Let $\mu_{N_i} = 1_N - \lambda_{N_i}$. Then $1_N - \lambda_N = \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} int(\mu_{N_i})$, where $cl(\mu_{N_i}) = 1_N$. \square

Proposition 3.4. *If $cl(\lambda_{N_i}) = 1_N$, where λ_{N_i} is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) , then λ_{N_i} is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_{N_i} be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) . Then $\lambda_{N_i} = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} cl(\lambda_{N_i})$, where $int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$. Now, $cl(\lambda_{N_i}) = 1_N$ implies that $cl(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} cl(\lambda_{N_i})) = 1_N$. But $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} cl(cl(\lambda_{N_i})) = 1_N$ implies that $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} intcl(cl(\lambda_{N_i})) = int(1_N)$. This implies that $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} intcl(\lambda_{N_i}) = 1_N$. Then $cl(\lambda_{N_i})$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Hence $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (cl(\lambda_{N_i}))$, where $(cl(\lambda_{N_i}))$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense sets, implies that λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 3.5. *If $cl(\lambda_N) = 1_N$, where λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) , then $1_N - \lambda_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic residual set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) such that $cl(\lambda_N) = 1_N$. Then by proposition-3.4, λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) , and hence $1_N - \lambda_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic residual set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Remark 3.6. :

Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) . Then we have, $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} cl(\lambda_{N_i})$, where $int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$. If (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic closed sets in (X_N, T_N) , then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) . For, if (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic closed sets, then $cl(\lambda_{N_i}) = \lambda_{N_i}$, implies that $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$, where $intcl(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$ and hence λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Also, since $int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$, (λ_{N_i}) 's are not fuzzy neutrosophic open sets in (X_N, T_N) .

Proposition 3.7. *If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_{σ} -set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) . Then, we have, $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} cl(\lambda_{N_i})$, where $int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$ and hence $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} cl(\lambda_{N_i})$, implies that λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_{σ} -set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 3.8. *If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) then $1_N - \lambda_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -set formed the fuzzy neutrosophic dense sets in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. The proof follows from proposition 3.7, The following proposition gives the condition for a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space to be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set. \square

Proposition 3.9. *If $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$, for a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set λ_N in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) , then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) such that $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Then by Proposition 3.7, λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set in (X_N, T_N) . Hence λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set such that $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Therefore λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 3.10. *If $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$, for a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set λ_N in a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) , then λ_N is not a fuzzy neutrosophic dense set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) such that $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Then by Proposition 3.9, λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) . Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space, by Theorem 2.23, λ_N is not a fuzzy neutrosophic dense set in (X_N, T_N) .

The following proposition ensures the existence of a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space. \square

Proposition 3.11. *If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) , then there exists a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set μ_N in (X_N, T_N) such that $\lambda_N \leq \mu_N$ in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Then $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) and hence $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$ where $\text{int} \text{cl}(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$. Now, $\text{int}(\lambda_{N_i}) \leq \text{intcl}(\lambda_{N_i})$, implies that $\text{int}(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$. Let $\mu_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} \text{cl}(\lambda_{N_i})$, where $\text{int}(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$. Then μ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense in (X_N, T_N) . Now, $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i}) \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} \text{cl}(\lambda_{N_i})$, implies that $\lambda_N \leq \mu_N$ in

(X_N, T_N) . Therefore, if λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space, then there exist a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set μ_N in (X_N, T_N) such that $\lambda_N \leq \mu_N$ in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 3.12. *If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic submaximal space (X_N, T_N) , then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic submaximal space (X_N, T_N) . Then $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} cl(\lambda_{N_i})$, where $int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$. Now, $int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$, implies that $cl(1_N - \lambda_{N_i}) = 1_N - int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 1_N$. Hence $(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic submaximal space, the fuzzy neutrosophic dense sets $(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic open sets in (X_N, T_N) and hence (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic closed sets in (X_N, T_N) . Then $cl(\lambda_{N_i}) = \lambda_{N_i}$. Now, $intclcl(\lambda_{N_i}) = intcl(\lambda_{N_i}) = int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$. Then $(cl(\lambda_{N_i}))$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Hence $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (cl(\lambda_{N_i}))$, where $(cl(\lambda_{N_i}))$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense sets, implies that λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 3.13. *If $int(\lambda_N) = 0_N$, for each fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set λ_N in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) , then (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic Baire space.*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Then by Proposition 3.11, there exists a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set μ_N in (X_N, T_N) such that $\lambda_N \leq \mu_N$ in (X_N, T_N) . By hypothesis, $int(\mu_N) = 0_N$. Now, $\lambda_N \leq \mu_N$, implies that $int(\lambda_N) \leq int(\mu_N)$. Then we have $int(\lambda_N) \leq 0_N$. That is, $int(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Hence by Theorem 2.24, (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic Baire Space. \square

Proposition 3.14. *If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) , then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic closed set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) . Then by Proposition 3.8, $1_N - \lambda_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -set in (X_N, T_N) . Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space, then the fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -set $(1_N - \lambda_N)$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic open set in (X_N, T_N) and hence λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic closed set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Definition 3.15. A fuzzy neutrosophic set λ_N in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category set if $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) .

Definition 3.16. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Then $1_N - \lambda_N$ is called a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -residual set in (X_N, T_N) .

Proposition 3.17. *If a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic almost resolvable space, then 1_{X_N} is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set.*

Proof. Let (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic almost resolvable space. Then, $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i}) = 1_N$, where the fuzzy neutrosophic sets (λ_{N_i}) 's in (X_N, T_N) are such that $\text{int}(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$. Now, $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i}) \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} \text{cl}(\lambda_{N_i})$, implies that $1_N \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} \text{cl}(\lambda_{N_i})$. That is $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} \text{cl}(\lambda_{N_i}) = 1_N$, where $\text{int}(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$. Hence 1_{X_N} is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set. \square

Proposition 3.18. *If $1_N - \lambda_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic closed and fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) , then $1_N - \lambda_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic closed and fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic open and fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) . Since λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set. By Proposition 3.8., $1_N - \lambda_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -set in (X_N, T_N) . Hence $1_N - \lambda_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic closed and fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 3.19. *If $1_N - \lambda_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic closed and fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) , then $1_N - \lambda_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let $1_N - \lambda_N$ be a fuzzy neutrosophic closed set and fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) . Since $1_N - \lambda_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) . By Proposition 3.7, $1_N - \lambda_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 3.20. *If $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$, for a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set λ_N in a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) , then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic open and fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) such that $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Then by proposition 3.14, λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic closed set in (X_N, T_N) and hence $\text{cl}(\lambda_N) = \lambda_N$. Now, $\text{intcl}(\lambda_N) = \text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$ and therefore λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

4. FUZZY NEUTROSOPHIC REGULAR σ -BAIRE SPACES

Definition 4.1. A fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space if $\text{int}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) .

The following proposition gives the characterization of fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space in terms of fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category sets and fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -residual sets in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space.

Proposition 4.2. Let (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space then the followings are equivalent.

- (1) (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space.
- (2) $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$, for every fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set λ_N in (X_N, T_N) .
- (3) $\text{cl}(\mu_N) = 1_N$ for every fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -residual set μ_N in (X_N, T_N) .

Proof. (1) \implies (2):

Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Then $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) and hence $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = \text{int}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i}))$. Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire Space, $\text{int}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$. Hence $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$, for a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category set λ_N in (X_N, T_N) .

(2) \implies (3):

Let μ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -residual set in (X_N, T_N) . Then $(1_N - \mu_N)$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) . By hypothesis, $\text{int}(1_N - \mu_N) = 0_N$. Then $1_N - \text{cl}(\mu_N) = \text{int}(1_N - \mu_N) = 0_N$. Hence $\text{cl}(\mu_N) = 1_N$, for a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -residual set μ_N in (X_N, T_N) .

(3) \implies (1):

Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Then $\lambda_N = (\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i}))$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Now, λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) , implies that $(1_N - \lambda_N)$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -residual set in (X_N, T_N) . By hypothesis,

$cl(1_N - \lambda_N) = 1_N$. Then $1_N - int(\lambda_N) = 1_N$ and hence $int(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. That is $int(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Hence (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space. \square

Proposition 4.3. *If a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space, then $cl(\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(\mu_{N_i})) = 1_N$, Where (μ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -sets formed from the fuzzy neutrosophic dense sets in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space. Then $int(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Now, $1_N - int(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})) = 1_N$, implies that $cl(\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})) = 1_N$. Since (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . By proposition 3.3, we have $1_N - \lambda_{N_i} = \bigwedge_{j=1}^{\infty} int(\mu_{N_{ij}})$, where $cl(\mu_{N_{ij}}) = 1_N$. Let $\delta_{N_i} = 1_N - \lambda_{N_i}$. Then (δ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -sets in (X_N, T_N) . Hence we have $cl(\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(\delta_{N_i})) = 1_N$, where (δ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -sets formed from the fuzzy neutrosophic dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 4.4. *If a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space, then (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic Baire space.*

Proof. Let (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space. Then $int(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Now, $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}[int(\lambda_{N_i})] \leq int[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})]$, implies that $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}[int(\lambda_{N_i})] \leq 0_N$. That is $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}[int(\lambda_{N_i})] = 0_N$. This implies that $int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$, for each i . Thus for the fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets (λ_{N_i}) 's in (X_N, T_N) . We have $int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$. Therefore by proposition 3.13, (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic Baire space. \square

Proposition 4.5. *If (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space, then $int(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic first category sets in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let (λ_{N_i}) 's be a fuzzy neutrosophic first category sets in (X_N, T_N) . Then by proposition 3.11, there exists fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets μ_{N_i} in (X_N, T_N) such that $\lambda_{N_i} \leq \mu_{N_i}$ in (X_N, T_N) . Then we have $int(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})) \leq int(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\mu_{N_i}))$. Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space, $int(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\mu_{N_i})) = 0_N$. Then, $int(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})) \leq 0_N$. That is $int(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$. Thus $int(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic first category sets in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 4.6. *If (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space, then (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic Baire space.*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Then $\lambda_N \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic first category sets in (X_N, T_N) in which $\lambda_{N_1} = \lambda_N$. Now, $\lambda_N \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$ implies that $\text{int}(\lambda_N) \leq \text{int}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i}))$. Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space. By proposition 4.5, $\text{int}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$. Then $\text{int}(\lambda_N) \leq 0_N$. That is, $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Hence we have $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$, for a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) and therefore, by Theorem 2.24, (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic Baire space.

□

Proposition 4.7. *If (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space, then (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space.*

Proof. Let (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space. Then, $\text{int}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Now, $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} [\text{int}(\lambda_{N_i})] \leq [\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})]$, implies that $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} [\text{int}(\lambda_{N_i})] \leq 0_N$. That is $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} [\text{int}(\lambda_{N_i})] = 0_N$. This implies that $\text{int}(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$, for each i . By proposition 3.9, (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Hence we have, $\text{int}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Therefore (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space. □

Definition 4.8. A fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category space if the fuzzy set 1_{X_N} is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) . That is, $1_{X_N} = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Otherwise, (X_N, T_N) will be called a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -second category space.

Proposition 4.9. *If a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category space, then $\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (\mu_{N_i}) = 0_N$, where (μ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic G_{δ} -sets formed from the fuzzy neutrosophic dense sets in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category space. Then, $1_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Now, $1_N - \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$. Then $\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (1_N - \lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$. since (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . By proposition 3.8, $(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic G_{δ} -sets formed from the fuzzy neutrosophic dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Let $\mu_{N_i} = (1_N - \lambda_{N_i})$. Then $\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (\mu_{N_i}) = 0_N$, where (μ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic G_{δ} -sets formed from the fuzzy neutrosophic dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . □

Proposition 4.10. *If a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space, then (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -second category space.*

Proof. Let (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space. Then, $\text{int}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Now, we claim that, $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i}) \neq 1_{X_N}$. Suppose that $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i}) = 1_{X_N}$. Then, this will implies that $\text{int}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})) = \text{int}(1_{X_N}) = 1_{X_N} \neq 0_N$, this is a contradiction. Hence we must have $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i}) \neq 1_{X_N}$ and (X_N, T_N) is not a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category space. Therefore (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -second category space. \square

Proposition 4.11. *If the fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category space, then (X_N, T_N) is not a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space.*

Proof. Let the fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category space. Then, $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i}) = 1_N$, where the fuzzy sets (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Now $\text{int}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})) = \text{int}(1_N) = 1_N \neq 0_N$. Hence (X_N, T_N) is not a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space. \square

Proposition 4.12. *If the fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space, then no non-zero fuzzy neutrosophic open set is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_N be a non-zero fuzzy neutrosophic open set in a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space (X_N, T_N) such that $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})$, where the fuzzy neutrosophic sets (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Then $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = \text{int}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i}))$. Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space, $\text{int}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$. This implies that $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Then we will have $\lambda_N = 0_N$, This is a contradiction. [Since $\lambda_N \in T_N, \text{int}(\lambda_N) = \lambda_N$ in (X_N, T_N)]. Hence $\lambda_N \neq \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})$ and therefore no non-zero fuzzy neutrosophic open set is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 4.13. *If the fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space, then (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic almost irresolvable space.*

Proof. Let (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space. By proposition 4.11, (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -second category space and hence (X_N, T_N) is not a fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -first category space. Then, $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i}) \neq 1_N$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are

fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) .

Now, $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} [int(\lambda_{N_i})] \leq int[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})]$, implies that $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} [int(\lambda_{N_i})] \leq 0_N$. That is, $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} [int(\lambda_{N_i})] = 0_N$. This implies that, $int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$, for each i . Hence $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i}) \neq 1_N$, where $int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$ and therefore (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic almost irresolvable space.

□

Remark 4.14. :

The relation between fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space, fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space and fuzzy neutrosophic almost irresolvable space, can be summarized as follows.

5. Conclusion

The study of fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire Spaces contributes significantly to the advancement of fuzzy neutrosophic topology by extending the classical notion of Baire spaces within the framework of uncertainty and indeterminacy. These spaces provide a robust structure where the interplay of fuzziness, neutrosophic logic and regularity conditions can be analyzed systematically. The key conclusion is that under appropriate conditions, the fuzzy neutrosophic regular σ -Baire space maintains essential topological properties such as density of fuzzy neutrosophic open sets and the preservation of σ -Baire conditions under regularity. This class of spaces has potential applications in areas where precise classification is impossible, such as decision-making, computational intelligence and Mathematical Modelling. Furthermore, the results offer a groundwork for further generalizations and investigations into fuzzy neutrosophic connectedness, compactness and continuity within more generalized space.

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